

Implementation of Adapted Physical Education Strategy during the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Role of Information Technology

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Keywords

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to determine the Implementation of Adapted Assessment Learning during the Covid-19 Pandemic. Participants in this study were 10 SLB teachers. The design used is phenomenology. The instruments used were observation, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis in a qualitative descriptive manner. The results of the study that adaptive assessment learning during the Covid-19 pandemic for adaptive physical education teachers experienced obstacles to the implementation of adaptive physical education practice learning because learning during the pandemic used online or online-based learning. Learning that is carried out online is one of the problem-solving in carrying out learning during this pandemic, but the role of parents is also very important for students with special needs for smooth learning at home so that education can run well. The contribution to the next research is the development and modification of learning plans that are in accordance with learning objectives in adaptive physical education subjects.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia affects all perspectives of life, one of which is Education. This pandemic also has an impact on education for children with special needs, namely adaptive physical education [1]. Adaptive physical education is education that is achieved through physical activity as the main means to achieve a goal and is adjusted or modified so that it can be learned, implemented and met with the needs of students with special needs [2,3]. Learning in Indonesia itself is currently applied is distance education using online-based educational media. Because education is carried out at home so that students want to be helped by parents and people at home.

During the pandemic, adaptive physical education teachers are increasingly required to be more creative and innovative in their academic achievements. The impact of the pandemic on adaptive learning has greatly affected students with special needs. As a result, learning is more focused on online learning. This is a big challenge for physical education teachers who teach in special schools. The problems experienced by adaptive

physical education teachers in extraordinary schools in online education are in facilities and infrastructure such as signals, online education media, educational applications, internet quotas and application-based education [4].

Adaptive physical learning during the Covid-19 pandemic requires teachers who usually teach directly to be switched to online learning. Of course, this learning goal will be achieved with the support of various parties, the urgency of the adaptive physical education learning setting carried out by adaptive physical education teachers is to modify learning during the pandemic and still follow the provisions of the RPP used. So, an adaptive physical education learning strategy is needed at home. The implementation of learning carried out during the Covid-19 pandemic includes assigning assignments to students with special needs that can be understood by students when learning at home [5,6].

Adaptive physical education is not just about learning how to participate in a particular sport that teaches students a variety of skills, but also how to work as a team when interacting in games, how to solve problems, improve concentration, and focus

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on task-based behaviors [7,8]. Therefore, parents and children are expected to learn from each other to adjust to new learning conditions, namely learning from home. Furthermore, adaptive physical education teachers, class teachers, homeroom teachers, and schools must also help so that students' learning activities at home run well. The importance of supporting and mentoring teachers and schools is certainly very significant for the success of learning.

Based on the description above, this article aims to explain how the process of implementing learning during the Covid-19 pandemic and provide the right solutions to existing problems in the learning applied so that students with special needs can continue to get good learning and develop even during the current Covid-19 pandemic.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study participants were selected using purposive sampling demands [9]. Thus, the sample in this study was 10 adaptive physical education teachers in Indonesia. The sample selected is considered capable of meeting the criteria for sampling requirements, namely: Adaptive physical education teachers active in the last three years, or who supervised adaptive physical education learning during the Covid-19 pandemic.

2.1. Research Design

The research design used is a qualitative method with a phenomenological approach. Phenomenological research is a study that aims to understand phenomena in the field by research subjects by means of descriptions in the form of words and language based on observations, for example seen from a point of view that occurs periodically and runs with qualitative methods generally carried out by way of description and in the form of interviews / observations and documentation [10].

2.2. Research Instruments

The collection of data or information used as material to be processed in this study includes observation, interviews, and documentation. Observations will contribute to the observed research or activity in a more structured record.

The observation technique is to directly see the location to be visited then see the learning process applied by adaptive physical education teachers at school. Observation includes the field of notes in research on the implementation of adaptive physical learning. The interview technique carried

out is a direct meeting with adaptive physical education teachers to get statements, opinions and data needed in research. The interview in this study is an intensive interview structured with the aim of obtaining in-depth qualitative data. The instrument used in the interview is an unstructured interview sheet that allows the researcher to get information from the adaptive physical education teacher in more depth.

The documentation carried out is in the form of pictures, activity documentaries, learning implementation plan documents (RPP) and data related to research. Supporting documents in this study are useful as reinforcement, support, complement, confirmation, to understand the results of research data, namely observation, and interviews. Supporting documents are also expected to further clarify, strengthen, and complement the data in this study.

2.3. Statistical Analysis

Data analysis in research is carried out using a descriptive approach. The steps in the analysis start from collecting data, reducing data, presenting data, verifying data, and finally drawing data conclusions. The first step, data collection is the first step because researchers must collect as much data as possible from the research revealed. The second step, data presentation is one of the activities of making research reports that have been carried out so that the data collected can be understood and analyzed in accordance with the desired purpose. The third step, data verification is the process of collecting research reports used in assessing the truth of theoretical foundations with facts in the field, which must then be processed and analyzed so that they can be tested using predetermined research. The fourth step, concluding is the end of the data analysis and processing phase.

3. RESULTS

This research focuses on the implementation of adaptive physical education learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. Interview results from 3 respondents at SLB. This learning study is seen from the implementation of learning strategies in accordance with learning strategies, methods, and modifications, while the implementation of learning is seen from the planning and implementation activities that have been implemented.

The implementation of learning strategies is seen from 3 aspects, namely strategies, methods, and learning modifications.

From the aspect of learning strategy, there are two indicators, namely conducting initial

assessment and selection of learning media. These two indicators have been met or carried out by all respondents (APE teachers). One of the APE teachers with the initials FE mentioned that:

"Learning during the pandemic is indeed very dynamic, but therefore we always conduct initial assessments before learning, even every time we change the material and choose media that suits the learning conditions".

There is only one indicator of the learning method aspect, namely the selection of learning methods. Based on the results of the interview, data was obtained that all physical education teachers in the Special School had made initial considerations before determining the online learning method. One APE teacher with the initials AM mentioned that:

"We have made initial considerations for each learning which includes consideration of online learning methods".

The learning modification aspect consists of three indicators, namely the use of curriculum, the fulfillment of infrastructure, and modifications to learning media. During this pandemic, all physical education teachers in Special Schools have made modifications both in terms of curriculum, infrastructure and learning media. One APE teacher with the initials SS mentioned that:

"APE learning was modified in various aspects during the pandemic, including infrastructure and media used".

There are three aspects of learning implementation, but in this study two of the three aspects are taken namely planning and implementation. The planning aspect consists of four indicators, namely learning implementation plans, teaching preparation, and infrastructure preparation. All indicators start from the preparation of lesson plans, preparation of online learning infrastructure during the pandemic. One of the APE teachers with the initials FE mentioned that "we have made initial considerations every time we do learning, including consideration of online learning methods"

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation with physical education teachers, the implementation of physical education learning during the Covid-19 pandemic is

carried out online, where physical education teachers must be able to prepare related to the design of learning plans in which there are physical education materials to be taught, from previously face-to-face learning to online learning.

Physical education learning in Special Schools has its own characteristics, where the material delivered by each individual is different, because each material given to each individual is useful for improving motor skills in certain body parts, but the material to be given is in accordance with the 2013 curriculum in Indonesia [5,11].

The implementation of adaptive physical education learning does not fully use KTSP and the 2013 curriculum, but can be adjusted to the conditions, needs, and abilities of students [12,13]. Adaptive physical education learning that is carried out aims to maintain physical fitness and health, train skills, confidence, discipline and as therapy.

Adaptive physical education teachers must choose the right strategy in implementing online learning by utilizing technology and maximizing the role of parents so that the learning process can run in accordance with learning objectives because teachers cannot meet face to face with students, besides that if physical education teachers cannot make the right strategy in learning, learning becomes ineffective and efficient in developing the ability of students with special needs.

Students with special needs have different characteristics from other normal students. They desperately need direction from a teacher. In addition, support from parents is also very influential, where the implementation of physical education learning before Covid-19 really needs assistance by parents. Parents help physical education teachers to move students according to the direction of the teacher, this is so that it can be practiced at home which is useful for honing the abilities of students where these abilities can be used in everyday life.

Adaptive sports are sports specifically designed for those who have limited abilities and use modified equipment, and education can instill a sense of security, foster individuality, and equip students with a wide range of skills [14,15].

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that the implementation of adaptive physical education learning during the Covid-19 pandemic is carried out by adjusting the situation and conditions of students with special needs. Cooperation between teachers and guardians is the key to successful learning. Advice that can be given related to this

research is that there is good cooperation from various parties. Smooth communication must also be built between teachers and guardians, so that it can help students in learning and ultimately learning goals can be achieved.

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Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest is declared by the authors. In addition, no financial support was received.

Ethics Committee

The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee from our University (Ethics Committee Approval with Number: 051/A/I/2022).

Author Contributions

First author: all contribution

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